

Title:

Analysis of Machine Tools Accuracy by Virtual Machining Systems

By:

Mohsen Soori

University:

Amirkabir University of Technology (Tehran Polytechnic), Tehran, Iran

Date:

18 November 2015

Supervisor:

Prof. **Behrooz Arezoo**

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Amirkabir University of Technology (Tehran Polytechnic)

Abstract: To increase accuracy as well as efficiency in part manufacturing, virtual manufacturing systems are presented by simulating production processes in digital environments. Thus, the modified operations of machine tools can increase added value in part manufacturing processes.

Keywords: Virtual Machining, Accuracy of Machine Tools

1- Introduction

Virtual manufacturing systems can provide useful means for products to be manufactured without the need of physical testing on the shop floor. As a result, the time and cost of part production can be decreased [1]. To modify process of part production by machine tools, virtual simulations are applied to the actual machining operations. Thus, accuracy of part manufacturing by using machine tools can be analyzed to be modified [2].

2- Applications

- To increase accuracy of part manufacturing, dimensional, geometrical and tool deflection errors of 3-axis CNC machine tools can be simulated and analyzed in virtual environments [1].
- Dimensional and geometrical errors of 3-axis CNC machine tools can be simulated and analyzed in virtual environments [2], [4].

- Accuracy of process of part production can be increased by applying the optimization to the simulated machining process in virtual environments [3].

References

- [1] Soori, M., Arezoo, B. and Habibi, M., 2014. Virtual machining considering dimensional, geometrical and tool deflection errors in three-axis CNC milling machines. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, 33(4), pp.498-507.
- [2] Soori, M., Arezoo, B. and Habibi, M., 2013. Dimensional and geometrical errors of three-axis CNC milling machines in a virtual machining system. *Computer-Aided Design*, 45(11), pp.1306-1313.
- [3] Soori, M., Arezoo, B. and Habibi, M., 2016. Tool Deflection Error of Three-Axis Computer Numerical Control Milling Machines, Monitoring and Minimizing by a Virtual Machining System. *Journal of Manufacturing Science and Engineering*, 138(8), pp. 081005.
- [4] Soori, M., 2012. Virtual Machining.